

Relativistic Energy and Momentum Representing Quantum Information in Space and Time? Part 2: Magnetic Potential

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In Part I, we argued that the Lorentz transformation is readily derivable for a particle with rest mass from space-time considerations. We also noted that it holds for a photon. (Here we try to argue that this is to be expected a priori.) In particular, for a particle with rest mass, one has $x=0$, t in the rest frame and $x'/t'=v$ in the moving (-v). For a photon one has: $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$. The same transformation holds for the spacetime (i.e. x,t) features for both.

We suggested in Part 1 that extending the use of the transformation to pc and E means that these interaction related variables have the same math or superficial appearance as x,ct . In other words, one sees a linear $x=vt$ type equation, except that it involves the variables p and E . One has to be careful, however, to include all c values because the overall velocity is of the form cc/v . Then, $constant/p$ is like Δx and $constant/E$, like Δt . The interaction variables E,p become spacetime gradations and this leads to ideas of quantum mechanics.

We argued in Part I that the key idea for extending the Lorentz transformation to p and E is that in the rest frame there is a variable t which always exists as well as an mo (for a particle with rest mass) which also always exists. In the moving frame, there is an x' which satisfies $x'=vt'$. Thus, the t variable becomes t' through the presence of v , but multiplied by v produces x' . Likewise, $v mo g(v) = p$, where $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. We suggest that there are similar ideas present linking (x,ct) and (pc,E) . This means that $\int p dx = \int dx (1/p)$ counts cycles in space which is information.

We suggest here that this way of thinking may be applied to the magnetic vector potential. In particular, $A = \mu_0/(4\pi) \int J / |r-r'| + dx dy dz$. $J=v$ density for a single particle moving with constant v and ϕ =electromagnetic potential = $1/(4\pi \epsilon_0) Q/r$. Thus: $A = v/cc \phi$ and the equation mimicking $x=vt$ is: $cc/v 1/\phi = 1/A$. Just like $\int p dx$, this suggests that $1/A$ is like a changing gradation in space and $\int dx A(x)$ is phase information just like $\int p dx$.

Lorentz Transformation as a Spacetime Transformation

We argued in Part 1 that the Lorentz transformation may be readily seen as a spacetime transformation for a particle with rest mass (and extended to a photon) because of the constraints;

$$x'/t' = v \quad (x=0, t \text{ in the rest frame}) \text{ for a particle with rest mass } ((1a))$$

$$x/t=c, \quad x'/t'=c \text{ for a photon } ((1b))$$

We showed that by using ((1a)) one readily obtains the transformation:

$$\begin{aligned} |g(v) \quad v g(v)| \quad ((2)) \quad g(v) &= 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \\ |v g(v) \quad g(v)| \end{aligned}$$

If one uses a particle with rest mass, the parameter b (with velocity units) instead of c appears and holds in all frames. One makes the choice to set $b=c$ and finds then that the transformation also satisfies ((1b)) for a photon. The reason that one should have the same transformation apply to both a photon and particle with rest mass is that the same spacetime applies to both. For example:

$$x=vt \text{ (particle with rest mass) and } x=ct \text{ (photon) ((3))}$$

Thus, even though ((1b)) does not contain v and it is readily possible to create the transformation ((1)) for a particle with rest mass, we argue here that a priori one should expect it to hold for a photon as well. Thus, setting $b=c$ is not an arbitrary choice, but is the one which allows ((1)) to apply to a photon as well as a particle with rest mass.

Lorentz Transformation Applied to E, p

We suggested in Part 1 that the Lorentz transformation could be applied to E and p which are interaction variables, not spacetime variables in Newtonian mechanics. This leads to important consequences because if pc, E are used in ((1)), then superficially at least they have the appearance of spacetime variables in the sense that an $x'=vt'$ type equation must appear, even though they are constants. One must have an equation analogous to:

$$x= vt \text{ ((4a)) namely; } 1/p = cc/v 1/E \text{ ((4b))}$$

$$((4b)) \text{ follows from; } p = m_0 v g(v) = v E/cc \text{ ((5))}$$

We argued that $\text{constant}/p = \Delta x$ and $\text{constant}/E = \Delta t$, meaning they are gradations that measure information in spacetime, i.e.

$$\text{Integral } p/\text{constant } dx \text{ and } \text{Integral } E/\text{constant } dt \text{ ((6))}$$

We argued above that the equations which hold for a particle should also apply to a photon. If one sets $v=c$ in ((5)), then one has:

$$E=pc \text{ ((7))}$$

Planck, however, argued that photon energy is: $\hbar w$, where \hbar is his constant (divided by 2π) and $w= 2\pi \cdot \text{frequency}$. Thus:

$$E = \hbar w \text{ and the idea of } \Delta t = \text{constant}/ E \text{ may be associated with } \text{constant}=\hbar w$$

if $1/w$ is taken as Δt .

The key assumption of these above ideas, however, is that pc and E really transform like x and t according to ((1)). In Part 1, we argued that for a particle with rest mass:

In the rest frame one has m_0 (rest mass) and time. One may set $x=0$ and $p=0$. It is only through the presence of v that one has $x'=vt'$ and $p= v^*(a \text{ masslike term})$. We argued that v is a switch for both x and p and that v is multiplied by a changed t or changed m_0 which exist in the rest frame. This was the reason given for allowing E and p to transform like x and t .

In the case of a photon, one has the experimental evidence that it behaves as a wave, hence:

$$c = \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength} \quad ((8))$$

Planck showed, however, that $E = hbar w$. Using this and ((8)) means that;

Wavelength = $hbar/p$ if one uses the Lorentz transformation, i.e. $E = pc + m_0 c^2$ (with $m_0=0$) for a photon.

We suggest that Planck's idea that photon energy is linked with a frequency ($hbar w$) is a key idea. This idea, however, seems to be identical to assuming that pc and E transformation according to the Lorentz transformation because this means that $constant/E = \Delta t$ and $constant/p = \Delta x$. $1/\Delta t$ may be considered a frequency equal to $E * constant^{-1}$. In fact, if one applies ((1)), the Lorentz transformation, to a photon, one finds that:

$$E=pc, \text{ but also that } E/hbar = \text{frequency and } p/hbar = 1/\text{wavelength} \quad ((9))$$

Thus, $E=pc$ is also the wave-equation ((8)), but is obtained strictly from applying the Lorentz spacetime transformation to pc and E . This, we argue, is why pc and E become related to frequency and wavelengths which is something that does not appear in Newtonian mechanics.

Magnetic Vector Potential

We now try to extend this idea to the vector magnetic potential. The reason we do so is because it follows the basic rest frame, v transformation pattern. In particular, in the rest frame there is an electrostatic potential:

$$\Phi = 1/(4*3.14*eo) a/R \quad ((10))$$

There is no magnetic vector potential in the rest frame. It is turned on if there is a v and one has the definition (1);

$$A = \mu_0/(4*3.14) \text{ Integral } J/|r-r'| dx dy dz \quad ((11))$$

((11)) will lead to an equation analogous to $x'=vt'$.

$J = v \cdot \text{charge density}$ so one has the correct linear v response, just like $x=vt$. One must, however, find the equation which mimics $x=vt$ by considering all velocity factors, i.e. v and all c 's.

Given that $c=1/\sqrt{\mu_0 \epsilon_0}$ ((12)) :

$$A(x) = v/c \phi \quad ((13)) \quad \text{so:} \quad c/v \cdot 1/\phi = 1/A \quad ((14))$$

((14)) is of the form: $c/v \cdot 1/E = 1/p$ so:

constant/A should measure changing gradations in space. This leads to:

$$\text{constant} \cdot \int A(x) dx = \text{number of cycles in space} \quad ((15))$$

We thus suggest that $A(x)$ is linked to gradations in space, like p , because it transforms like a 4-vector, together with ϕ . We suggest that it transforms (according to the Lorentz transformation) because of the linear $v \cdot \phi$ form in the moving frame, just like $x'=vt'$ (also in the moving frame). Thus, an equation of the form:

$$B = v \cdot N' \text{ in the moving frame,}$$

where $B=0$ and N exists and is linked to N' in the rest frame suggests one has a Lorentz transformation and that B and N are now linked to spacetime.

Usual Approach to A, the Magnetic Vector Potential

The traditional approach (1) to dealing with the magnetic vector potential is to write:

$$H = \text{Hamiltonian} = 1/2m (p - qA) \cdot (p - qA) + q\phi \quad ((16))$$

One then treats p and qA as being similar mathematically and so if $\int p dx$ is phase, then so is: $-q \int A \cdot dx$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Lorentz transformation is very much linked to the spacetime form: $x'=vt'$ for a rest mass (hence rest frame case). The transformation, however, also holds for photons. We suggest that one may apply the Lorentz transformation to other pairs of variables or constants if one of these, A , is 0 in the rest frame, but the other, B , exists. In the moving frame one should have: $A = v \cdot B'$, where B' is related to B . If this is the case, then one may consider applying the spacetime Lorentz transformation to A and B . If this is fine, one may find an equation analogous to $x'=vt'$, but must be careful to include all c values. Hence, for $p = (v/c) E$ one has: $1/p = c/v \cdot 1/E$ and $\text{constant}/p = \Delta x$ and $\text{constant}/E = \Delta t \cdot 1/\Delta t$,

however, is like a frequency and Planck showed that $E = \hbar \omega$, so constant = \hbar so that the theory is consistent with photons. Here we show that these ideas may be applied to the magnetic vector potential because for a point charge and constant v : A (magnetic potential) = $v/c \phi$ (electric potential), so constant/ A is like a changing gradation in space and $\int A(x) dx$ measures cycles in space just like $\int p dx$.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Magnetic_vector_potential